

A Common Fixed Point Theorem For Generalized Contraction Pair Of Sefmaps In B-Metric Spaces

Alemayehu Negash^{1*}, Abebaw Ayalew² and Meaza Bogale³

Abstract

This paper establishes a common fixed point theorem for a pair of self-maps satisfying a generalized contraction condition in the framework of b -metric spaces. Unlike traditional metric spaces, b -metric spaces allow a relaxation of the triangle inequality, enabling the study of a broader class of spaces such as ℓ^p and $L^p[0, 1]$ for $0 < p < 1$. Motivated by recent developments in fixed point theory, particularly those involving generalized Ciric-type contractions, we introduce a novel contraction criterion and investigate the existence and uniqueness of common fixed points under this setting. The analytical techniques adopted for the successful completion of this study are based on the methods of Sarwar and Rahman, and Roshan et al. Our results extend and unify several existing fixed point theorems in the literature, offering new insights into the structure of mappings in generalized metric-type spaces. Examples are provided to demonstrate the applicability of the main theorem.

Keywords

Common fixed point, b -metric space, generalized contraction, occasionally weakly compatible maps.

^{1,3}Department of Mathematics, Hampton University, USA .

²Department of Mathematics, Jimma University, Ethiopia.

*Corresponding author: alemayehu.negash@hamptonu.edu

1. Introduction

Fixed point theory is a fundamental area in nonlinear functional analysis, offering powerful tools for solving a wide range of problems across mathematics and applied sciences. The pioneering work of Banach [1] on contraction mappings laid the foundation for this field. His celebrated fixed point theorem guarantees the existence and uniqueness of fixed points for self-mappings in complete metric spaces and ensures convergence via Picard iteration. Over the decades, this classical result has inspired numerous generalizations to broader classes of mappings and more generalized spaces.

Notable extensions include the Kannan [2] and Chatterjea [3] fixed point theorems, which relax the contractive condition while still ensuring the existence of fixed points under suitable assumptions. Rhoades [4] provided a comprehensive comparative study of various types of contractive mappings, leading to further developments such as Ciric-type generalized

contractions[5] and integral-type contractive conditions [6, 7].

Alongside these generalizations, considerable effort has been made to extend the underlying spaces themselves. While every metric space is a special case of a b -metric space, the converse does not hold. The notion of a b -metric space, introduced by Czerwik [8], relaxes the triangle inequality by introducing a multiplicative constant $k \geq 1$, thereby accommodating a wider class of spaces, including ℓ^p and $L^p[0, 1]$ spaces for $0 < p < 1$. Theoretical advances in this setting have led to significant results for both single-valued and multivalued mappings [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14].

More recently, Sarwar and Rahman [7] established a b -metric space version of generalized Ciric-type contraction principles, paving the way for the analysis of more flexible contractive conditions in generalized settings. Motivated by their work, we investigate the existence and uniqueness of common fixed points for a pair of self-maps satisfying a

generalized contraction condition in the context of b -metric spaces.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [8] Let X be a non-empty set and $k \geq 1$ be a real number. A mapping $d : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is called a b -metric if for all $x, y, z \in X$, the following conditions hold:

$$(D1) \quad d(x, y) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = y,$$

$$(D2) \quad d(x, y) = d(y, x),$$

$$(D3) \quad d(x, y) \leq k [d(x, z) + d(z, y)].$$

The pair (X, d) is then called a b -metric space. From the above definition it is evident that the b -metric space extended the metric space. Here, for $k = 1$ it reduces into standard metric space. But the converse is not true as clear from the following examples.

Example 2.2. [15] Let

$$\ell_p = \left\{ x = \{x_n\} \subset \mathbb{R} \mid \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |x_n|^p < \infty \right\}, \quad 0 < p < 1,$$

and define

$$d(x, y) = \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |x_n - y_n|^p \right)^{1/p}, \quad x, y \in \ell_p.$$

We show that (ℓ_p, d) is a b -metric space with constant $k = 2^{1/p}$, but not a metric space.

(D1) and (D2): Clearly

$$d(x, y) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = y, \quad d(x, y) = d(y, x).$$

(D3): For any $x, y, z \in \ell_p$, set

$$u_n = x_n - z_n, \quad v_n = z_n - y_n,$$

so $x_n - y_n = u_n + v_n$. Then

$$|x_n - y_n|^p = |u_n + v_n|^p \leq 2(|u_n|^p + |v_n|^p).$$

Summing over n and taking the $1/p$ -power gives

$$\begin{aligned} d(x, y) &= \left(\sum |x_n - y_n|^p \right)^{1/p} \\ &\leq 2^{1/p} \left[\left(\sum |u_n|^p \right)^{1/p} + \left(\sum |v_n|^p \right)^{1/p} \right] \\ &= 2^{1/p} [d(x, z) + d(z, y)]. \end{aligned}$$

Hence d satisfies the relaxed triangle inequality with $k = 2^{1/p}$.

Non-metric remark:

Since $p < 1$, the ordinary triangle inequality fails, so (ℓ_p, d) is not a metric space.

Example 2.3. Let $L^p[0, 1]$ be the space of real-valued functions $x(t)$ such that $\int_0^1 |x(t)|^p dt < \infty$, with

$$d(x, y) = \left(\int_0^1 |x(t) - y(t)|^p dt \right)^{1/p}$$

Verification of (D3): Let $u(t) = x(t) - z(t)$ and $v(t) = z(t) - y(t)$:

$$|x(t) - y(t)|^p = |u(t) + v(t)|^p \leq 2(|u(t)|^p + |v(t)|^p)$$

Integrating:

$$\int_0^1 |x(t) - y(t)|^p dt \leq 2 \int_0^1 (|u(t)|^p + |v(t)|^p) dt$$

Using Minkowski inequality:

$$d(x, y) \leq 2^{1/p} (d(x, z) + d(z, y))$$

So, $L^p[0, 1]$ with this d is a b -metric space with $k = 2^{1/p}$.

Example 2.4 ([10]). Let $L^p[0, 1] = \{x : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid \int_0^1 |x(t)|^p dt < \infty\}$ with $0 < p < 1$. Define

$$d(x, y) = \left(\int_0^1 |x(t) - y(t)|^p dt \right)^{1/p} \quad \text{for all } x, y \in L^p[0, 1].$$

We show that $(L^p[0, 1], d)$ is a b -metric space with constant $k = 2^{1/p}$, but not a metric space.

Verification of (D1) and (D2):

Clearly $d(x, y) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = y$, and $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$.

Verification of the relaxed triangle inequality (D3):

For any $x, y, z \in L^p[0, 1]$, set

$$u(t) = x(t) - z(t), \quad v(t) = z(t) - y(t),$$

so $x(t) - y(t) = u(t) + v(t)$. Then for each t ,

$$|x(t) - y(t)|^p = |u(t) + v(t)|^p \leq 2(|u(t)|^p + |v(t)|^p).$$

Integrating and taking the $1/p$ -power:

$$\begin{aligned} d(x, y) &= \left(\int_0^1 |x - y|^p \right)^{1/p} \\ &\leq 2^{1/p} \left[\left(\int_0^1 |u|^p \right)^{1/p} + \left(\int_0^1 |v|^p \right)^{1/p} \right] \\ &= 2^{1/p} [d(x, z) + d(z, y)]. \end{aligned}$$

Thus d satisfies

$$d(x, y) \leq k [d(x, z) + d(z, y)] \quad \text{with } k = 2^{1/p}.$$

Therefore $(L^p[0, 1], d)$ is a b -metric space.

Non-metric remark:

When $p < 1$, the ordinary triangle inequality fails, so $(L^p[0, 1], d)$ is not a metric space.

Example 2.5 ([9]). Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$. Define $d: X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ by

$$\begin{aligned} d(2, 0) &= d(0, 2) = m \geq 2, \\ d(0, 1) &= d(1, 0) = d(1, 2) = d(2, 1) = 1, \\ d(x, x) &= 0 \quad (\forall x \in X). \end{aligned}$$

We claim that (X, d) is a b -metric space with constant $k = \frac{m}{2}$, but is not a metric space when $m > 2$.

Verification of the b -metric inequality:

For any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$d(x, y) \leq \frac{m}{2} [d(x, z) + d(z, y)].$$

One checks each of the finitely many cases directly; for instance, if $x = 2, y = 0, z = 1$, then

$$d(2, 0) = m \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{m}{2} [d(2, 1) + d(1, 0)] = \frac{m}{2} (1 + 1) = m,$$

so $d(2, 0) \leq \frac{m}{2} [d(2, 1) + d(1, 0)]$. Similar checks cover all other triples.

Failure of the ordinary triangle inequality:

Take $x = 2, z = 1, y = 0$. Then

$$d(2, 0) = m > 2 \quad \text{but} \quad d(2, 1) + d(1, 0) = 1 + 1 = 2,$$

so $d(2, 0) > d(2, 1) + d(1, 0)$. Thus (X, d) does not satisfy the standard triangle inequality when $m > 2$.

Therefore, (X, d) is a b -metric space with $k = \frac{m}{2}$, yet not a metric space for $m > 2$.

Example 2.6 ([16]). Let (X, d) be a metric space and fix $p > 1$. Define

$$f(x, y) = (d(x, y))^p, \quad x, y \in X.$$

We claim that f is a b -metric on X with constant $k = 2^{p-1}$, but that (X, f) need not be a metric space.

Verification of (D1) and (D2):

$$\begin{aligned} f(x, y) &> 0 \quad \text{for } x \neq y, \\ f(x, y) &= 0 \iff d(x, y) = 0 \iff x = y, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$f(x, y) = d(x, y)^p = d(y, x)^p = f(y, x).$$

Verification of the relaxed triangle inequality (D3): Since $g(t) = t^p$ is strictly convex on $(0, \infty)$, one has

$$(a + b)^p \leq 2^{p-1} (a^p + b^p) \quad \forall a, b \geq 0.$$

Thus for any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$\begin{aligned} f(x, y) &= d(x, y)^p \\ &\leq (d(x, z) + d(z, y))^p \\ &\leq 2^{p-1} (d(x, z)^p + d(z, y)^p) \\ &= 2^{p-1} (f(x, z) + f(z, y)). \end{aligned}$$

Hence f satisfies

$$f(x, y) \leq k [f(x, z) + f(z, y)] \quad \text{with } k = 2^{p-1},$$

so (X, f) is a b -metric space.

Non-metric example: Take $X = \mathbb{R}$ with the usual metric $d(x, y) = |x - y|$ and $p = 2$. Then

$$f(x, y) = (x - y)^2$$

is a b -metric on \mathbb{R} with $k = 2$, but fails the ordinary triangle inequality, so it is not a metric.

Definition 2.7 ([7]). Let (X, d) be a b -metric space. A sequence (x_n) in X is called *Cauchy* if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$d(x_n, x_m) < \varepsilon \quad \text{for all } m, n \geq N.$$

Definition 2.8 ([7]). A sequence (x_n) in a b -metric space (X, d) is said to *converge* to $x \in X$ if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$d(x_n, x) < \varepsilon \quad \text{for all } n \geq N.$$

In this case, x is called the *limit* of (x_n) .

Definition 2.9 ([7]). A b -metric space (X, d) is said to be *complete* if every Cauchy sequence in X converges to a point of X .

Remark 2.10. In any b -metric space (X, d) , the following hold:

1. Every convergent sequence has a unique limit.
2. Every convergent sequence is Cauchy.
3. The b -metric need not be continuous, since not every b -metric space is a metric space.

Definition 2.11 ([4]). Let (X, d) be a metric space. A self-map $T: X \rightarrow X$ is called a *generalized contraction* if there exists $h \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq h \max \left\{ d(x, y), d(x, Tx), d(y, Ty), \frac{1}{2} [d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)] \right\}$$

for all $x, y \in X$.

Theorem 2.12 ([13]). Let (X, d) be a complete b -metric space with coefficient $k \geq 1$, and let $T: X \rightarrow X$ satisfy

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq h d(x, y), \quad h \in [0, 1), kh < 1.$$

Then T has a unique fixed point in X .

Definition 2.13 ([16]). Two self-maps $f, T: X \rightarrow X$ of a metric space (X, d) are called *compatible* if for every sequence (x_n) with

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f x_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T x_n = t,$$

one has

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(f T x_n, T f x_n) = 0.$$

Example 2.14 ([16]). Let $X = [0, \infty)$ with the usual metric. Define

$$f(x) = x^5, \quad T(x) = \frac{1}{2}x^5.$$

Then

$$d(fx, Tx) = \frac{1}{2}|x|^5 \rightarrow 0 \iff x \rightarrow 0,$$

and

$$d(Tfx, fTx) = \frac{15}{32}|x|^{25} \rightarrow 0 \iff x \rightarrow 0,$$

so f and T are compatible.

Definition 2.15 ([17]). Let $f, T: X \rightarrow X$. A point $x \in X$ is a coincidence point of f and T if $f(x) = T(x)$. The set of all coincidence points is denoted by $C(f, T)$.

Definition 2.16 ([17]). f and T are weakly compatible if they commute at each coincidence point, i.e.

$$fTx = Tfx \quad \text{for all } x \in C(f, T).$$

Definition 2.17 ([17]). f and T are occasionally weakly compatible if there exists at least one $x \in C(f, T)$ for which

$$fTx = Tfx.$$

Example 2.18 ([16]). Let $X = [1, \infty)$ equipped with the usual metric. Define the self-maps:

$$f(x) = 4x - 3, \quad T(x) = x^2.$$

We seek the coincidence points of f and T , i.e., points $x \in X$ such that $f(x) = T(x)$. Solving:

$$4x - 3 = x^2 \implies x^2 - 4x + 3 = 0 \implies (x - 1)(x - 3) = 0.$$

Thus, the only coincidence points are $x = 1$ and $x = 3$.

Now evaluate the compositions $Tf(x)$ and $fT(x)$ at these points:

- At $x = 1$:

$$Tf(1) = T(1) = 1, \quad fT(1) = f(1) = 1.$$

Hence, $Tf(1) = fT(1)$, and the maps commute at the coincidence point $x = 1$.

- At $x = 3$:

$$Tf(3) = T(9) = 81, \quad fT(3) = f(9) = 33.$$

So, $Tf(3) = 81 \neq 33 = fT(3)$, and the maps do not commute at the coincidence point $x = 3$.

Therefore, f and T are occasionally weakly compatible (OWC), since there exists at least one coincidence point (namely $x = 1$) where they commute. However, they are not weakly compatible (WC), as there exists a coincidence point (namely $x = 3$) where they fail to commute.

3. Main Results

Lemma 3.1. Let (X, d) be a b -metric space with constant $k \geq 1$, and let $\{y_n\}$ be a sequence in X such that

$$d(y_n, y_{n+1}) \leq \alpha d(y_{n-1}, y_n) \quad \text{for all } n \geq 1,$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1)$ and $\alpha k < 1$. Then $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X .

Proof. We first prove by induction that for all $n \geq 1$,

$$d(y_n, y_{n+1}) \leq \alpha^n d(y_0, y_1).$$

For $n = 1$, we have

$$d(y_1, y_2) \leq \alpha d(y_0, y_1) = \alpha^1 d(y_0, y_1),$$

which establishes the base case.

Suppose that for some $n \geq 1$,

$$d(y_n, y_{n+1}) \leq \alpha^n d(y_0, y_1).$$

Using the recursive inequality,

$$\begin{aligned} d(y_{n+1}, y_{n+2}) &\leq \alpha d(y_n, y_{n+1}) \\ &\leq \alpha^{n+1} d(y_0, y_1). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the inequality holds for $n + 1$, completing the induction. Hence, for all $n \geq 1$,

$$d(y_n, y_{n+1}) \leq \alpha^n d(y_0, y_1).$$

Now, we show that $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. Let $\varepsilon > 0$ be given. Since $\alpha \in [0, 1)$, the sequence $\alpha^n d(y_0, y_1)$ tends to zero as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, there exists $N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n \geq N$,

$$\alpha^n d(y_0, y_1) < \frac{\varepsilon(1 - \alpha k)}{k}.$$

Let $m > n \geq N$. We apply the b -metric inequality repeatedly to estimate $d(y_n, y_m)$. By iterated application of the inequality

$$d(x, z) \leq k[d(x, y) + d(y, z)],$$

one shows by induction that

$$d(y_n, y_m) \leq \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} k^{j+1} d(y_{n+j}, y_{n+j+1}).$$

Using the bound on $d(y_{n+j}, y_{n+j+1})$ from earlier, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} d(y_n, y_m) &\leq \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} k^{j+1} \cdot \alpha^{n+j} d(y_0, y_1) \\ &= d(y_0, y_1) \cdot \alpha^n \cdot \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} (k\alpha)^j \cdot k \\ &= k \alpha^n d(y_0, y_1) \sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} (k\alpha)^j. \end{aligned}$$

Since $k\alpha < 1$, the geometric series converges, and we have:

$$\sum_{j=0}^{m-n-1} (k\alpha)^j \leq \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (k\alpha)^j = \frac{1}{1-k\alpha}.$$

Therefore,

$$d(y_n, y_m) \leq \frac{k\alpha^n d(y_0, y_1)}{1-k\alpha} < \varepsilon.$$

Thus, for all $m > n \geq N$, $d(y_n, y_m) < \varepsilon$, proving that $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . \square

Theorem 3.2. Let (X, d) be a complete b -metric space with constant $k \geq 1$, and let $f, T : X \rightarrow X$ be self-maps satisfying:

- (a) $T(x) \subseteq f(x)$ for all $x \in X$;
- (b) each $f(x)$ is closed;
- (c) f and T are occasionally weakly compatible;
- (d) there exists $h \in [0, 1)$ with $kh < 1$ such that for all $x, y \in X$,

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq h \max \left\{ d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty), \left[\frac{1}{2k} [d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)] \right] \right\}$$

Then f and T have a unique common fixed point in X .

Proof. Choose an arbitrary $x_0 \in X$. Since $T(x_0) \subseteq f(x_0)$, we have $T(x_0) \in f(x_0)$. Hence there exists $x_1 \in X$ such that

$$f(x_1) = T(x_0) =: y_0.$$

Inductively, having $x_n \in X$ with $y_{n-1} = T(x_{n-1}) = f(x_n)$, we choose $x_{n+1} \in X$ so that

$$f(x_{n+1}) = T(x_n) =: y_n.$$

Thus we obtain the sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X and define

$$y_n := T(x_n) = f(x_{n+1}), \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

We call $\{y_n\}$ the Jungck sequence associated to x_0 .

We consider:

Case 1. There exists n_0 such that $y_{n_0} = y_{n_0+1}$.

Then

$$y_{n_0} = T(x_{n_0}) = f(x_{n_0+1}) \quad \text{and} \quad y_{n_0+1} = T(x_{n_0+1}) = f(x_{n_0+2}),$$

so

$$f(x_{n_0+1}) = f(x_{n_0+2}) \implies T(x_{n_0+1}) = f(x_{n_0+1}),$$

i.e. x_{n_0+1} is a coincidence point: $x_{n_0+1} \in C(f, T) \neq \emptyset$. By occasional weak compatibility, there exists $u \in C(f, T)$ with

$$f(T(u)) = T(f(u)).$$

Set $w := f(u) = T(u)$. Then

$$f(w) = f(T(u)) = T(f(u)) = T(w).$$

We now show w is a fixed point of both:

If $T(w) \neq w$, apply the contraction on $x = w$, $y = u$:

$$d(Tw, Tu) \leq h \max \left\{ d(fw, fu), d(fw, Tw), d(fu, Tu), \left[\frac{1}{2k} [d(fu, Tv) + d(fv, Tu)] \right] \right\}$$

Since $fw = Tw = w$ and $fu = Tu = w$, every term inside the max equals $d(Tw, w)$. Hence

$$d(Tw, Tu) = d(Tw, w) \leq h d(Tw, w),$$

so $(1-h)d(Tw, w) \leq 0$. With $d \geq 0$ and $h < 1$, it follows $d(Tw, w) = 0$, i.e. $Tw = w$. Thus $w = f(w) = T(w)$.

Therefore, w is a common fixed point.

Case 2. $y_n \neq y_{n+1}$ for all n . Then for each $n \geq 0$, applying the contractive condition with $x = x_n$, $y = x_{n+1}$ gives

$$d(y_n, y_{n+1}) = d(Tx_n, Tx_{n+1}) \leq h \max \left\{ d(fx_n, fx_{n+1}), d(fx_n, Tx_n), d(fx_{n+1}, Tx_{n+1}), \left[\frac{1}{2k} [d(fx_n, Tx_{n+1}) + d(fx_{n+1}, Tx_n)] \right] \right\}.$$

But $fx_n = y_{n-1}$, $Tx_n = y_n$, $fx_{n+1} = y_n$, $Tx_{n+1} = y_{n+1}$. Hence

$$d(y_n, y_{n+1}) \leq h \max \left\{ d(y_{n-1}, y_n), d(y_{n-1}, y_{n+1}), \left[\frac{1}{2k} [d(y_{n-1}, y_{n+1}) + d(y_n, y_n)] \right] \right\}.$$

Suppose, for contradiction, that the maximum term is $d(y_n, y_{n+1})$. Then from the contraction condition:

$$d(y_{n+1}, y_n) \leq h \cdot d(y_n, y_{n+1})$$

Since all terms are distinct, $d(y_n, y_{n+1}) > 0$, so we can divide both sides: $1 \leq h$. This contradicts our hypothesis that $h \in [0, 1)$. Therefore, our initial assumption must be false, and $\max \neq d(y_n, y_{n+1})$.

The maximum must then be either:

$$d(y_n, y_{n-1}) \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{1}{2k} d(y_{n-1}, y_{n+1}).$$

By the b -metric property:

$$d(y_{n-1}, y_{n+1}) \leq k [d(y_{n-1}, y_n) + d(y_n, y_{n+1})]$$

Substituting back:

$$\frac{1}{2k} d(y_{n-1}, y_{n+1}) \leq \frac{1}{2} [d(y_{n-1}, y_n) + d(y_n, y_{n+1})]$$

Since $d(y_n, y_{n+1})$ cannot be the maximum, the dominant term must be:

$$d(y_n, y_{n-1})$$

leading to the key contraction:

$$d(y_{n+1}, y_n) \leq hd(y_n, y_{n-1})$$

for every n . Thus

$$d(y_n, y_{n+1}) \leq h^n d(y_0, y_1).$$

Now $kh < 1$, so by Lemma 3.1, $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. Completeness of X gives

$$y_n \rightarrow y \quad \text{in } X.$$

Since $y_n = f(x_{n+1})$ and each $f(x_{n+1}) \in f(X)$, and $f(X)$ is closed, the limit y lies in $f(X)$. Thus there is $u \in X$ with

$$f(u) = y.$$

On the other hand $y_n = T(x_n) \rightarrow y$ and $T(x_n) \in T(X) \subseteq f(X)$; by closedness of $f(X)$ again $y \in T(X)$. Hence

$$y \in f(u) \cap T(v) \quad \text{for some } v,$$

giving $y \in C(f, T)$. Occasional weak compatibility now yields

$$f(y) = T(y).$$

An identical contraction argument as in Case 1 shows $y = f(y) = T(y)$. Hence y is a common fixed point.

Suppose $q \neq y$ is another common fixed point. Then

$$d(y, q) = d(Ty, Tq) \leq h \max\{d(fy, fq), \dots\} = hd(y, q),$$

so $(1-h)d(y, q) \leq 0$, forcing $d(y, q) = 0$. Thus $y = q$.

Combining both cases, we conclude that f and T have exactly one common fixed point in X . \square

Example 3.3. Let $X = [0, 2]$ be endowed with the b-metric $d(x, y) = |x - y|^2$, for all $x, y \in X$, and let $s = 2$. Define the mappings $f, T : X \rightarrow X$ by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq 1, \\ 2 & \text{if } 1 < x \leq 2, \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad T(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } 1 < x \leq 2. \end{cases}$$

We observe that $f(X) = f([0, 2]) = [0, 1] \cup \{2\}$ is closed. Since $f(1) = T(1) = 1$, the self-maps f and T are occasionally weakly compatible.

Now we verify whether f and T satisfy inequality (4.4) of Theorem 4.2.2.

Case 1: If $x, y \in [0, 1]$ or $x, y \in (1, 2]$, then it is straightforward to verify that the inequality (4.4) holds.

Case 2: Let $x > 1, y \in [0, 1]$, and $h = \frac{1}{2}, k = 1$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx, Ty) &= |0 - 1|^2 = 1, \\ d(fx, fy) &= |2 - y|^2 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{2}d(fx, fy) = \frac{1}{2}(2 - y)^2, \\ d(fx, Tx) &= |2 - 0|^2 = 4 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{2}d(fx, Tx) = 2, \\ d(fy, Ty) &= |y - 1|^2 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{2}d(fy, Ty) = \frac{1}{2}(1 - y)^2, \\ \frac{1}{2k}[d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)] &= \frac{1}{2}[|2 - 1|^2 + |y - 0|^2] \\ &\Rightarrow h \cdot \frac{1}{2k}[d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)] = \frac{1}{4}(1 + y^2). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq h \cdot \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty), \\ &\frac{1}{2k} [d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)] \end{aligned} \right\}.$$

Case 3: Let $x \in [0, 1], y > 1$, and again $h = \frac{1}{2}, k = 1$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx, Ty) &= |1 - 0|^2 = 1, \\ d(fx, fy) &= |x - 2|^2 \Rightarrow h \cdot d(fx, fy) = \frac{1}{2}(2 - x)^2, \\ d(fx, Tx) &= |x - 1|^2 \Rightarrow h \cdot d(fx, Tx) = \frac{1}{2}(1 - x)^2, \\ d(fy, Ty) &= |2 - 0|^2 = 4 \Rightarrow h \cdot d(fy, Ty) = 2, \\ \frac{1}{2k}[d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)] &= \frac{1}{2}[|x - 0|^2 + |2 - 1|^2] \\ &\Rightarrow h \cdot \frac{1}{2k}[d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)] = \frac{1}{4}(x^2 + 1). \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq h \cdot \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &d(fx, fy), d(fx, Tx), d(fy, Ty), \\ &\frac{1}{2k} [d(fx, Ty) + d(fy, Tx)] \end{aligned} \right\}.$$

Hence, inequality (4.4) holds in all cases.

Therefore, f and T satisfy all the conditions of Theorem 4.2.2, and so $x = 1$ is the unique common fixed point of f and T .

Corollary 3.4. Let (X, d) be a complete b-metric space with coefficient $k \geq 1$ and T be a self-mapping on X satisfying the condition

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq h \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &d(x, y), d(x, Tx), d(y, Ty), \\ &\frac{1}{2k} [d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)] \end{aligned} \right\}$$

for all $x, y \in X$, where $h \in [0, 1)$ and $kh < 1$. Then T has a unique fixed point.

Proof. Taking f as identity map on X and applying Theorem 4.2.2, we get the required result. \square

Remark 3.5. Corollary 4.2.3 is the result of Sarwar and Rahman [27]. This Remark shows that, Theorem 4.2.2 is an extension of Theorem 1.9.

Corollary 3.6. Let (X, d) be a complete metric space with coefficient and T be a self-mapping on X satisfying the condition

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq h \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &d(x, y), d(x, Tx), d(y, Ty), \\ &\frac{1}{2} [d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)] \end{aligned} \right\}$$

for all $x, y \in X$, where $h \in [0, 1)$, then T has a unique fixed point.

Proof. Taking f as identity map on X and $k = 1$. Then we get the required result by applying Theorem (3.1). \square

Remark 3.7. Corollary 4.2.4 is the result of Rhoades [4].

4. Conclusion

In 2015, Sarwar M. and Rahman M.U [7] established the existence of unique fixed point results for mapping satisfying the generalized contraction in b-metric space. In this research work, we have established the existence of a unique common fixed point for generalized contraction pair of selfmaps in b-metric space. Also, we have supported our main result of this research work by example. Our work extends the main result in [7].

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